

Effect of sheath rot on some yield components

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We studied the effect of sheath rot (ShR) on some yield components in an irrigated field of four plots planted to IR442-2-58 that was severely infected with *Sarocladium oryzae* Gams and Hawks.

Fifty plants per plot were randomly selected and evaluated for disease incidence. Individual tillers of each plant were rated using a 3-infection level scale (see figure). Healthy panicles made up 20.8% of the sample, 19.8% were in category 1, 13.5% in category 2, and 45.9% in category 3.

For further evaluation, 200 panicles from each disease severity category were harvested. Number of spikelets/panicle, percent filled spikelets/panicle, weight of filled grains/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight were recorded.

Percent filled spikelets/panicle was the yield component most affected by the disease, with only 2.7% recorded at scale 3 (see table). Number of spikelets/panicle and 1,000-grain weight were also significantly less for severely diseased panicles than for healthy ones. ShR significantly reduced yield per panicle and yield loss increased with increased severity.

Based on the measurements for yield/panicle within each disease severity category, and on the frequency of each category in the plots, the total yield loss associated with the disease was 52.8%. □

Severity rating scale (0 = healthy, normal panicle exertion, no discoloration or very few grains discolored; 1 = small brown lesions covering about 1/10 of leaf sheath, panicle exertion apparently normal, few grains discolored; 2 = larger lesions which tend to coalesce and may cover less than half the leaf sheath, about 65% or more panicle exertion, moderate grain discoloration; 3 = lesions have coalesced and may cover entire leaf sheath, no exertion to slight exertion of about 30% straight upward panicle, severe discoloration with whitish fungal growth).

Yield components of panicles with various sheath rot severity ratings.

Severity rating	1,000-grain wt (g)	Spikelets/panicle	Filled spikelets (%)	Relative yield (%)
0	24.9 a	164.2 a	95.0 a	100
1	24.3 a	178.5 a	90.7 a	88.3
2	22.3 b	171.4 a	59.8 b	62.4
3	14.8 c	144.5 b	2.7 c	1.2

^aHealthy and diseased panicles of IR442 selected in the field. Means in columns followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level.

Effect of herbicides on neck blast infection and rice yield

N. I. Singh, junior pathologist, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Wangbal, Manipur, India

Herbicides have been known to increase susceptibility of various plants to fungal and viral diseases. We studied the effect of herbicides commonly used in rice production on severity of neck blast (NBI) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, weed population, and rice yield in the field during

Effect of herbicides on NBI infection, weed population, and yield, Wangbal, Manipur, India.^a

Herbicide treatment	Application rate (kg ai/ha)	Weeds/m ²	Infection (%)	Yield (t/ha)
2,4-D	1.00	80	26.20 (30.64)	2.21
Fluchloralin	0.80	88	24.33 (29.46)	2.23
Pendimethalin	1.50	94	26.12 (30.67)	2.21
Oxyfluorfen	0.10	75	41.20 (39.90)	1.92
Thiobencarb	1.00	42	50.50 (45.09)	1.80
Butachlor	1.50	63	33.70 (35.47)	2.11
Untreated and nonweeded control		141	20.06 (26.60)	2.97
Weed-free check		0	16.95 (24.32)	3.60
CD (5%)			7.99	0.97

^aMean of three replications. Angular transformed values are in the parentheses.

1982 kharif. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Punshi was the test variety.

Six granular herbicides were broadcast 5 days after transplanting. Untreated and

nonweeded plots were the control. Weeds/m² were counted at harvest and disease intensity was scored using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Thiobencarb controlled weeds best, followed by butachlor. However, heavy

NBI infection was observed in thiobencarb-treated plots, which resulted in the lowest yield (see table). Increased NBI infection may have been caused by changes in the metabolic processes of the rice plants. □

Effect of fungicides on neck blast infection and rice yield

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Neck blast (NBI) of rice caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious problem in Manipur. We studied the relative efficacy

of six fungicides for NBI control in wet fields in 1982.

Fungicides carbendazim, benomyl, ziram, captafol, mancozeb, and edifenphos were sprayed at tillering, leaf booting, and just after flowering. Control plots were sprayed with sterile water. Percent infected panicles was calculated at maturity. Edifenphos-treated plots had no infection and yielded most, followed by those treated with ziram (see table). □

Effect of fungicides on NBI and yield, mean of three replications, Wangbal, Manipur, India.

Fungicide	Application rate (kg or liters/ha)	Infection (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Carbendazim	0.5	12.1	2.35
Benomyl	0.5	4.3	2.67
Ziram	2.5	3.6	2.91
Captafol	2.0	23.5	2.05
Mancozeb	2.5	21.1	2.10
Edifenphos	1.0	0	3.50
Control		27.2	1.95

Association of two types of virus particles in an isolate of rice tungro disease

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Late planted Jaya exhibited 90 to 100% tungro disease incidence in Orissa during 1982 kharif. Disease identity was established by transmission tests of the vector *Nephotettix virescens*. We studied tungro-infested plants under an electron microscope at the CNRA.

Dip preparations in 1% neutral phosphotungstic acid (PTA), made from sap of

different parts of infected leaves, were observed under an EM 300 Philips electron microscope. Isometric virus particles about 28 nm in diam and bacilliform virus particles measuring about 33 nm in diam and 175 nm long were observed (see figure). In different samples, bacilliform virus particles and isometric virus particles were in ratios 1:10 and 1:11. Observations indicated that both isometric and bacilliform virus particles are associated with severe tungro symptoms in the Cuttack isolate, which also is true for isolates from several other South and Southeast Asian countries.

Observations using negative coloration of samples, made from crude sap of infected leaves in PTA, indicate a lower percentage of bacilliform particles than of isometric particles. However, our electron microscope observations of

Electron micrograph showing tungro isometric (I) and tungro bacilliform (B) virus in dip preparations from leaf sap infected with rice tungro disease from Cuttack, India. Virus particles were negatively stained with 1% neutral PTA (magnification 54000 X).

purified virus preparations indicated that negative staining with PTA does not allow a correct estimate of the two types of virus particles, perhaps because PTA preparations damage bacilliform particles. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Some common predators of rice insect pests in Assam, India

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Assam is a tropical rain forest area with green vegetation throughout the year. Rainfall is 1,400-1,800 mm, humidity averages 85-95%, and temperature is 20-30°C during the monsoon (Jun-Sep), which is the main rice growing season. Monsoon conditions favor rice cultiva-

tion, pest multiplication, and the proliferation of their natural enemies. Predators, particularly arthropods, are abundant and play a significant role in controlling major insect pests of rice.

From 1980 to 1982, we evaluated monsoon rice to determine the role of